

Grammar Against Humanity: How Does Grammatical Incongruity Affect Perceptions of Humour?

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Abstract. Incongruity theory is one of the reigning theories of humour, explaining why we find jokes ‘funny’ — its argument is that humour comes from the unexpected. Prior linguistic studies of humour focus on semantic incongruity, that is when the meaning of the ‘punchline’ is unexpected from the ‘set up’ of the joke (as is the case with puns, irony, and double entendre joke-constructions). However, this prior research does not explore other kinds of incongruity such as grammatical incongruity. Memes are a great contemporary example of grammatical incongruity in humour such as Jeremy Clarkson (The Grand Tour, 2022) exclaiming ‘A egg!’ The question is raised, does the comedy come from his untraditional use of the consonant-predicating indefinite article *a* rather than the vowel predicating *an*, or the unexpected response? This project explores the relevance of grammatical incongruity for humour perceptions. Specifically, it seeks to understand if grammatical incongruity can improve, negate, or create a barrier to perceptions of humour in fill-in-the-blank joke constructions. To achieve this, a digital questionnaire based on the popular card game Cards Against Humanity is used to assess participants perceptions of grammatically incongruous joke-constructions and determines through quantitative and qualitative analysis that without semantic resolution it negates but with semantic resolution it can improve perceptions of humour.

Keywords: humour; grammar; grammatical incongruity

1 Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of humour, joke constructions mirror societal changes and technological advancements. As described by Holt (2004) the joke ‘is a form of humour that comes and goes with the rise and fall of civilizations.’ The features of joke-constructions, and what makes them ‘funny’ also shifts with cultural perspectives. David Crystal (2019, p. 97) notes that memes, a product of digital communication, demonstrate an innovative use of nonstandard grammar in multi-modal joke constructions. This dissertation questions whether the familiarisation with nonstandard grammar in memes has influenced humour trends and made using nonstandard grammar a method of crafting successful joke-constructions.

In this dissertation, data collected from a digital questionnaire based on the card game Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011) is used to assess whether grammatical incongruity negates, improves, or creates a barrier to perceptions of humour. After introducing key concepts, incongruity theory, my motivations, and Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011), I will outline my methodology, the key data, and analyse my findings. Overall, I show that grammatical incongruity often has a negative impact on whether fill-in-the-blank joke-constructions are perceived as humorous. However, this is impacted by a few factors: error eye-detection, the grammatical flexibility of the incongruity type, and whether or not the incongruity can be resolved.

2 Background

There are a few assumptions and key concepts that need to be established as they are the foundations of this research. This includes introducing a definition of humour, how it can be measured, and the

elements that contribute to its perception. I will also discuss David Crystal's Netspeak (2001) and how it creates a link between these fundamental aspects of humour and memes.

2.1 A Definition of Humour and Laughing at the Unexpected

Attardo (1994, p. 3) discusses the interdisciplinary issue of defining 'humour' for research and makes three conclusions: it is not productive to create theoretical differentiations of humour types (e.g. comic, ridiculous, mockery), laughter is not a successful defining criteria for humour perception, and the use of a 'humour competence' (Raskin, 1985 as cited in Attardo, 1994, p.12) is most successful as a 'working solution' (1994, p. 3). Attardo (1994, p. 196) summarises Raskin's idea of a 'humour competence': 'Because a speaker can tell if a sentence belongs to the set of grammatical sentences, argues Raskin, the speaker can tell if a text is funny or not [...] considering a text humorous is merely being aware of its perlocutionary goal and/or effect'. Arguably then, finding something humorous is something that can often be self-assessed by the individual. Therefore, using self-assessment may be an appropriate method of collecting data.

Another significant issue is the cause of humour perception; Attardo (1994, p. 14) conducts a survey of the literature on this topic. He argues that incongruity theory is the most productive for linguists as an essentialist argument (1994, p. 2). Incongruity theory is the most suitable framework for my project as I focus on grammatical incongruities that are unexpected and unexplainable. Eagleton (2019, p. 67) describes incongruous humour as 'a clash of incongruous aspects [...] a momentary defamiliarizing of the familiar.' Suls (1972, p. 85) provides a 'Humor-appreciation model' to illustrate this effect. To best explain this model, using cognitive 'script' terminology can be useful, but as this has many different definitions across the linguistic discipline I will operate on Attardo's (1994, pp.198-200): 'A script is an organized chunk of information about something', more specifically, 'a cognitive structure internalized by the speaker which provides the speaker with information on how things are done, organized, etc. [...] it contains information which is typical, such as well-established routines and common ways to do things and to go about activities.' In example (1) the reader will have an expectation based on their KNIGHTED script which may link to other scripts such as DIGNITY, FORMALITY, HONOUR.

- (1) 'your trousers falling down while you are being knighted.' (Eagleton, 2019, p. 67)

Juxtaposition is then created by a second TROUSERS FALLING DOWN script, which may link to other scripts like EMBARRASSMENT and INDECORUM. Suls (1972, p. 87) suggests that at 'this point one engages in problem solving to find how the punch line follows from the main body of the joke'. In example (1) this is a case of irony; the reader can see how awkward that situation might be and potentially find it humorous due to how unlikely it might be.

Suls' model has been a useful starting point for further frameworks. However, Suls argued that if there is no logic connecting the two expectations this will result in 'puzzlement' (1972, p. 85), which fails to account for absurdist humour. Attardo (2002, p. 27) argues that incongruous elements of joke-constructions 'may or may not be fully or in part (playfully or not) resolved by the occurrence of the punch line', and Kierkegaard argues a 'contradiction between expectation and experience' (2009 quoted in Couder, 2019, p. 5) can create humour perception. This raises the argument that incongruous aspects can be humorous despite lacking a logical connection. This research does not create purposeful logical connections between set ups and punchlines, which further tests this theory.

2.2 Cartoons, Memes, and Netspeak

Additionally, whilst Suls (1972, p. 85) was concerned with understanding the cognitive appreciation of joke-constructions in cartoons, this dissertation is inspired by memes. To apply Suls' model (1972, p. 85) to appreciating memes, it has to be noted how memes work in online communication. David Crystal (2001, p. 25) noted that the majority of scholars referred to Netspeak as written down spoken language but observed that the language differed from written and spoken language conventions. Instead, he offered up Netspeak which had its own rules and conventions, which further differed in different mediums. He notes the difference between online webpages and chatrooms where 'The situations are not all equally 'spoken' in character. We 'write' e-mails, not 'speak' them. But chatgroups are for 'chat' and people certainly 'speak' to each other there' (Crystal, 2001, p. 29). Crystal (2019, p. 97) discusses memes and notes they are shared digitally and the 'chief linguistic feature is the use of nonstandard forms — in early chat developments such as text messaging, chiefly deviant spelling; in more recent varieties, deviant grammar.' Therefore, memes act more similarly to standard spoken language conventions than written, and this often includes nonstandard grammar. This dissertation questions whether familiarisation with meme joke-constructions, and their nonstandard grammar, could have created a trend in joke-constructions leading to people appreciating grammatical incongruity in joke-constructions outside of the meme medium.

Today, physical printed cartoons have declined in popularity. I argue that the same positionality is now carried by internet memes that are 'often used to channel humour on the internet and on social media' (Tacharungroj & Nueangjamnong, 2015, p. 289). Trends in joke-constructions change with societal preferences. This can be supported by a case study of two cartoons from *Punch* (*Punch*, 1841-2002) magazine published over 60 years apart. *Punch* (*Punch*, 1841-2002) was a highly popular magazine, credited with bringing the term cartoon into the mainstream (Applebaum & Kelly, 1981) making it a reliable source for considering popular societal trends in cartoon joke-constructions. Figure 1 is an example of a comic cartoon in *Punch* (*Punch*, 1841-2002) magazine from 1902.

Using Suls' framework (1972, p. 85) there is an expectation created that the fisherman is reading the name of the boat but juxtaposed by his misreading of it. A semantic resolution is available if the fisherman is assumed to not know the word *psyche*. The humour comes when the viewer understands that phonetically *ps* could be pronounced /f/, *y* could be pronounced /i/ and *che* should be pronounced /ʃ/. It requires problem solving on the part of the viewer.

Figure 2 shows a later example from *Punch* magazine (*Punch*, 1841-2002), a cartoon about the 'British Car Industry' (Lemmings, 2022) published in 1977.

Figure 1: *Critical* (Punch, 1920, p. 6).

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Image details Mini cars driving off the cliffs of Dover into water.] — Editor’s Note

Figure 2: *1970s British Car Industry Cartoons from Punch magazine* (Lemmings, 2022).

Here the problem solving requires contextual information outside what is shown in the cartoon — it depicts Mini cars driving off the cliffs of Dover, because between 1969 and 1973 Mini’s gained popularity overseas and they began manufacturing them outside of England (Adams, 2024). An expectation is created but only resolved with contextual information. Overall, Figure 1 and Figure 2 show a difference in joke-construction style, with one requiring problem solving and the other requiring contextual information. There is a scarcity of research on the history of joke-constructions and the change to their semantic incongruity resolution. However, I think as suggested by Figure 1 and Figure 2 and Holt (2004) there are trends, and this dissertation questions whether grammatical incongruity could be a current trend started by joke-constructions in memes.

Across the last four decades memes with grammatical incongruities are common, as supported by Crystal (2019, p. 97).

Figures 3, 4 and 5 provide cross-decade examples of this comedic trend. Particularly Figures 4 and 5 were observed by Crystal as ‘Among the most successful inventions’ in memes with nonstandard grammar. Figure 1 was originally a translation error for the video game *Zero Wing* (Toaplan, 1992 as cited in Dubs, 2009) but Figures 4 and 5 are examples of Lolspeak — a variant of Crystal’s Netspeak (2001). Fiorentini observes the ‘nonstandard orthography, morphology and syntax’ of Lolspeak and its ‘extreme variability’ (2013, p. 1). I think that those who saw Figure 4 and 5 outside of their community

context may find them examples of absurdist humour. The scholars previously referred to (Suls, 1972; Attardo, 1994) focused on semantic incongruities within joke constructions, but this comedic trend raises a question of whether grammatical incongruities also affect perceptions of humour. To my knowledge, this has not been a previous consideration for the study of humour.

Figure 3: *All Your Base are Belong To Us* (Dubs, 2009).

Figure 4: *Happy Cat* (Menning, 2010).

Figure 5: *Doge* (NovaXP, 2014) .

2.3 Cards Against Humanity

Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011) is a popular card game; six days after its release on Amazon it became the number one game sold (Kickstarter, 2012), and over six thousand copies sold last month in America at the time of writing (Amazon, 2024).

The game consists of a white and black deck of cards. Each black card has a ‘question or fill-in-the-blank phrase’ acting as the set-up for joke-constructions; each white card has a word or phrase that ‘fills in the blank’ or ‘answers the question’, acting as the punchline (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2024). Players have a hand of white cards and must choose the funniest option to play, then a designated player will choose the winning white card (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2024).

The simplicity of this game made it feasible for me to manipulate joke-constructions to be grammatically incongruous. Suls (1972, p. 84) notes that ‘adults need to know they are hearing a joke: other incongruous situations may not be suitable stimuli for humor.’ Therefore, using a joke-construction card game adheres to this caveat. The participants may also be more familiar with evaluating how humorous they found joke-constructions if they have played Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011) before. Additionally, Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011) (often takes inspiration from memes which might make grammatical incongruities appear less obvious.

Any white card can grammatically fit with any black card, but they may make less semantic sense and Suls’ appreciation model (1972, p. 85) indicates they would be unresolvable. For example:

- (2) Black Card: Toys bore me, and I don’t care for sweets I prefer ____
- a. a wet, cold, slice of garlic bread.
 - b. Me, your dad.

Answer (2a), a wet, cold, slice of garlic bread would make more semantic sense as an answer to (2) than (2b), me your dad, as (2b) entails the impossible situation of the speaker being their own father. Therefore, other incongruities may be less apparent as participants familiar with the game would be used to semantic incongruities occurring and helping to avoid demand characteristic biases (Rhul, 2023).

3 Methodology

This section outlines the creation and implementation of the digital questionnaire used to collect data for this research dissertation, and how the design will allow me to answer my research questions. To reiterate, the key research questions for this dissertation are:

- Does grammatical incongruity in fill-in-the-blank joke constructions improve, negate, or create a barrier to perceptions of humour?
- Does incongruity type affect the answer to the first question?

There will also be further considerations into the questions:

- Grammatical incongruity is successful in memes, has this established a new comedic trend whereby grammatical incongruity is now acceptable in another digital medium?

This section will discuss the card game framework in a digital medium, the incongruity types chosen, the two types of question chosen, and the sample, as well as discussing limitations and their impact throughout.

3.1 Making a Card Game into a Questionnaire

The Cards Against Humanity original edition includes offensive humour. Thus, to protect the safety of participants and maintain ethical standards I used the family edition, which is designed to be inoffensive. From this deck I further removed white cards with brands, American expressions, and pop culture references as participants who couldn't contextualise them may have biases towards the other options. I only included fill-in-the-blank black cards, and removed questions or double blank ones, for feasibility.

For the first question set I used the chosen fill-in-the-blank black cards as the question and gave three white cards to choose from as the answers. The game is designed for every white card to fit any black card drawn. The white cards take the form of nouns, noun phrases, and gerund phrases. I chose three types of grammatical incongruity that would require minor modifications to the cards based on this. I also factored in which kinds of grammatical incongruity appeared in Figures 3, 4, and 5, as they represent successful grammatically incongruous joke-constructions.

Davies (2019) observes the impact survey fatigue can have on the integrity of digital questionnaire responses. To negate survey fatigue: I completed pilot tests to make sure the survey would not take longer than 15 minutes to complete, ensured consistency in question design and formatting, and did not include open text questions. Another impactful factor was participants consciously or subconsciously noticing and responding to the grammatical incongruities inconsistently with how they would naturally as a result of demand characteristics (Ruhl, 2023). The multiple-choice section of the questionnaire had 24 questions in total, with eight for each incongruity type. To lessen the likelihood of demand characteristics being detected by participants, six of the 24 questions had only congruous options to conceal what features were being investigated.

3.1.1 Articles

Jeremy Clarkson exclaimed 'A egg!' in a viral video, using the consonant predicating form of the indefinite article a rather than an. This example of grammatical incongruity was simple to apply to the white cards as several had noun phrases that included the indefinite article a, such as: 'A horse with no legs', or 'A corn dog' (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2024). For each question in the article section of the first question set, I added the indefinite article a to a black card and chose synonyms that began with vowels to be the incongruous option, this can be seen below in example (3).

- (3) The aliens are here. They want a ____.
- a. enormous honkin carrot
 - b. big wet kiss from Great Aunt Sharon
 - c. glorious beard

Example (3) is the first article question on the questionnaire. Answer (3a), enormous honkin carrot, is incongruous. Answers (3b) and (3c), big wet kiss from Great Aunt Sharon and glorious beard, are congruous. The congruous counterpart for (3a) was huge honkin carrot. The incongruous counterparts for (3b) and (3c) were enormous wet kiss from Great Aunt Sharon and amazing beard. I chose white cards with noun phrases on them that included an adjective as the first word to make finding synonyms simpler and less semantically impactful. Other synonyms included infant for child, old man for pensioner and oily for greasy - see appendix to view the other synonyms chosen.

3.1.2 Gerunds

As with the Doge meme shown in Figure 5 in the previous section, using an incongruous verb form is a common way of incorporating grammatical incongruity into memes. Such as ‘concern’ (NovaXP, 2014) rather than this is concerning, or I am concerned. As several white cards used gerunds this was straightforward as I could change the -ing suffix for -ed or remove it entirely, see example (4) below.

- (4) This is gonna be the best sleepover ever. Once Mum goes to bed, it’s time for _____.
- a. do maths
 - b. stuffing my underwear with pancakes
 - c. seeing Aunt Linda

Example (4) is the first question of the gerund section. Answer (4a), do maths, is incongruous. Answers (4b), stuffing my underwear with pancakes, and (4c), seeing Aunt Linda, are congruous. In example (4a) I removed the -ing suffix making it incongruous. For answers (4b) and (4c) they became stuffed and see. Other examples of this include braiding becoming braid or being becoming be - see appendix to view the rest of the changes made to white cards in the plural section.

3.1.3 *Plurals*

This section was not inspired by a meme but was chosen due to its feasibility for the cards available. I added quantifiers to the black cards such as plenty of or many which would then require a plural noun. Example (5) demonstrates this:

- (5) When I look in the mirror, I see many _____.
- a. teeny tiny turd
 - b. bears
 - c. old people

I then adjusted the white card options to be plural or singular. Thus, answer (5a), teeny tiny turds, became teeny tiny turd, (5b), bears, became bear and (5c), old people, became old person. Despite being chosen for feasibility this section had some errors which I will consider in the analysis section of this dissertation.

3.2 **A Semantically Incongruous Results**

If a white card was perceived as amusing because of semantic meaning it may be chosen more often despite grammatical incongruity. To be able to cross-compare individual white cards’ incongruous and congruous forms I created three versions of the questionnaire that rotated which white card was incongruous. I randomised the order of questions and white cards for participants, to offset the effect of demand characteristics which would be heightened if the incongruous option was always in the same place in the answer order.

Additionally, I included a second section to the questionnaire that asked participants to rate joke-constructions on a scale of 1-5. Figure 6 shows the basic layout that was repeated for each possible answer.

The rating scale question set was divided into two sets of 54 statements, separating the incongruous and congruous versions of constructions randomly so participants wouldn’t rate both

versions of one example. Out of 54, 12 statements were randomly distributed to each participant. Two pilot tests were conducted, one on someone who reads for pleasure who completed the questionnaire in nine minutes and another on someone who does not read for pleasure who completed it in 14 minutes; this supported minimising survey fatigue.

The rating scale question set allows for cross-comparison of congruous and incongruous forms of white cards. In the first question set participants are comparing three white card options, whilst in the rating scale question set, they evaluate them individually. Therefore, I was able to see which cards were chosen most often for each question, and if there were any where the incongruous form was preferred, I could then compare these specific statements with their rating in the second section to view if they were rated higher than their congruous forms. If the incongruous form was not rated higher than their congruous counterparts, it is likely that they were the most amusing semantically and this was more important to perceptions than their grammatical incongruity.

How amusing do you find these possible pairings to the previous question?

	Not amusing	Not very amusing	Neutral	Slightly amusing	Very amusing
The aliens are here. They want a huge honkin' carrot.	<input type="radio"/>				
Papa, come quickly! There, in the garden! Do you see a old guy respecting people's boundaries? Tell me you see it Papa!	<input type="radio"/>				
Come on, Danny. All the cool kids are doin' them. You should try those hunky man.	<input type="radio"/>				

Figure 6: *Example of Rating Scale Question*

3.3 The Sample

There were 100 responses, but some were removed due to incompleteness leaving 76 usable responses. Meyerhoff, Schleef and MacKenzie (2015, p. 78) recommend a sample size of at least 30 for normal distribution. To monitor potential sample bias and take social variables into account I requested participants 'age' and 'gender-identity' in the questionnaire. There were 25 men, 47 women and four non-binary people. 37 participants were between 18 and 39, and the other 39 were between 40 and 79. To take this into account my following analysis uses relative frequency when referring to results.

I would also note that whilst an argument could be made that younger participants may be more exposed to the grammatical incongruities in memes, the majority of the Lolspeak memes were popular between 2005 and 2010 (Dubs, 2009), making anyone between the ages of 30 and 50 possibly more exposed. Additionally, this questionnaire was shared on six social media platforms meaning the sample was those most likely to use those platforms. Therefore, this research is not a suitable assessment for

that hypothesis or a comparison of social media users and non-social media users. This dissertation only concerns a general impact on humour perception. Whether the impact of grammatical incongruity on humour perception differs between specific groups is beyond the scope of this project, but the social variables will be considered for a preliminary idea of these further questions.

This methodology was limited by a few errors made in the questionnaire due to missed autocorrected white cards, and a missing question from the rating section. These errors have caused some questions to be removed from the data pool but otherwise do not impact the analysis. Also, the flexibility of plural nouns was underestimated in design, but this overlook provided some interesting opportunities for cross-comparison particularly regarding construal.

4 The Data and Preliminary Analysis

This section will identify useful data from the questionnaire responses. Here, I will discuss the overall results, and in subsequent sub-sections I will discuss the results for each incongruity type (articles, gerunds, and plurals). Finally, I will identify the key takeaways.

For clarity, note that the order of white card options for the first question set was randomised for participants and is only relevant for the analysis. In the following graphs, ‘congruous 1’ refers to the option preceding the incongruous card in the analysed order, while ‘congruous 2’ refers to the subsequent option, which changes depending on which version of the questionnaire was answered. Therefore, comparison between ‘congruous 1’ and ‘congruous 2’ is irrelevant.

Figure 7 shows the overall results for which option was chosen in the multiple-choice question set.

Figure 7: Overall Results.

Overall, the congruous options were chosen 15-25% more than the incongruous, which is a notable amount. This suggests that grammatical incongruity may have a negative effect on perceptions of humour. However, when considering each incongruity type these results differ

The mean rating for the joke-constructions overall, congruous, and incongruous forms included, was 2.8 which provides a point of comparison for evaluating if a joke-construction did particularly well. The overall mean rating for incongruous options was 2.5 (out of 5), and the mean rating for congruous

options was 3.1 (out of 5). The rating data can be useful for cross comparing congruous and incongruous versions, and both the mode and mean will be used in the subsequent analysis of each incongruity type.

Overall, age and gender as social variables show no significance, this was tested using a Chi Square test both for the overall data and individual data sets for the three incongruity types. The p value was consistently above 0.04, thus suggesting no statistical significance for the results. As aforementioned, this sample may be biased as it targeted social media users, and those who likely follow language interest pages. To assess the impact of social variables on humour perception of grammatically incongruous joke-constructions, further research involving a more diverse sample would be necessary to determine any statistically significant differences. As such, the social variables will not be further considered in this analysis.

4.1 Gerunds

The gerund results showed the least preference for incongruous options.

Figure 8: Gerunds *Multiple Choice Question Data*.

Figure 8 shows that the incongruous form was selected 13% of the time, which is a notable decrease from the overall results. Thus, incongruous verb forms may be more of a barrier to humour perception than the other incongruity types.

Additionally, the rating scale data showed a near uncontested agreement that congruous forms were preferred over their incongruous counterparts. There was one outlying result that had the same mean rating for both the congruous and incongruous form, the results question can be seen below in example (6).

- (6) Kids dad is trying something new this week, it's called ' ___ '.
- eating cocktail weenies
 - eat cocktail weenies

Both answers for example (6) had a mean rating of three. However, the mode was four for the congruous form, eating cocktail weenies, and three for the incongruous form, eat cocktail weenies. As three was the neutral point this means that most participants considered the congruous form somewhat amusing

and the incongruous form neutral. Additionally, both answers could have been interpreted congruously because of the quotation marks. Quotation marks expect integrity to what is being referenced, therefore it's possible that errors would be leniently received (American Psychological Association 2022). If example (6) was interpreted congruously it would have been an anomalous result.

4.1.1 *Gerunds, Characterisation and Error Detection*

The gerund incongruity type was the least popular of the three types studied, but the most common in the Happy Cat and Doge memes as shown in Figures 4 and 5. This disparity raises the question of why the inspiring memes were successful and the joke-constructions on this questionnaire were not. Whilst the questionnaire style, length, sample or Cards Against Humanity framework are factors, I argue that the negative results are due to error-tracking and a lack of incongruity resolution without a character.

Larigauderie, Guignouard and Olive (2020) conducted research on error-tracking and the impact of memory on different types of errors. Overall, they determined that 'orthographical errors had the lowest rate of detection', followed by grammatical errors and then phonological errors (2020, p. 1030). Changing the verb form would be a grammatical error according to their guidelines (Larigauderie et al, 2020, p. 1020). As such, the verb form incongruity type in the questionnaire was the most likely to be noticed. Therefore, the gerund incongruity type results may show the sincerest attitudes towards nonstandard grammar in joke-constructions as there is less chance of misreading and assuming congruity was intended.

Additionally, the memes that inspired this incongruity type such as Happy Cat in Figure 4 and Doge in Figure 5, both have characters speaking with grammatical incongruities. The memes show cats and dogs using incongruous verb forms and adjectives such as 'concern' (NovaXP, 2014), or 'I can has cheezburger' (Menning, 2010). Suls' two-stage model suggests that the script of ANIMAL and THOUGHT would be activated in these memes. The script of THOUGHT and ANIMAL individually do not imply grammatical incongruities will occur, but they do, creating a complication. However, a semantic resolution is available whereby animals cannot speak English, but if they could their language may be nonstandard. The viewer can resolve the incongruity, and rather than reach puzzlement be open to perceiving the joke-construction as amusing.

Additionally, considering the medium of the meme versus the medium of the questionnaire, the conditions of Netspeak may have been affected. Crystal (2001, p. 25) observed that an issue with prior contributions to the study of language on the internet was 'Write the way people talk' sounds sensible enough, until we have to answer the question: which people?' Here Crystal notes the plethora of variations of spoken language, and thus the mass-variation of internet language that would exist if this was true. If the speaker in the Doge (NovaXP, 014) and Happy Cat (Menning, 2010) memes is being near-transcribed, and this is considered grammatically standard for the medium, then their joke-constructions may be entirely congruous. As Netspeak is partially based on spoken language, particularly in chatrooms where memes are shared, then in this instance the animal is the 'speaker' and thus in the memes the language may appear congruous as it represents the hypothetical real language. In the questionnaire, it would not appear that way as there is no visually identifiable speaker, or if there is such as 'Dad' from example (6) there is no logical resolution for why their language would be grammatically nonstandard.

To summarise, the gerund-incongruity type results indicate that in multimodal joke-constructions the character using grammatically incongruous language is important to whether it improves or negates perceptions of humour, and different digital mediums could impact this success. Additionally, grammatical incongruities appear to create a barrier to humour perception and can lead to puzzlement unless resolution occurs.

4.2 Articles

The article incongruity type showed the highest rate of preference for the grammatically incongruous forms.

In Figure 7 the incongruous option accounts for nearly a third of choices, showing less negation to humour perception than the gerund incongruity type. The data from the rating scale question shows that 65% of incongruous options were rated lower than their congruous counterparts, but only by 0.1-0.6 which is far less a disparity than the gerund incongruity type displayed. Furthermore, the mode for both incongruous and congruous options was four. Thus, both congruous and incongruous grammatical forms were considered somewhat amusing by most participants.

Figure 7: *Articles Multiple Choice Data.*

Example (7) had the lowest mean rating for congruous option, bothersome kid, with 1.7 (out of 5). Example (7a), annoying kid, was rated 2.25 in contrast.

- (7) The warm August air was filled with change. Things were different, for Kayla was now a ____.
- annoying kid
 - bothersome kid

Both means indicate they were not perceived as amusing, but bothersome kid was notably less so. There is the possibility that the synonyms chosen annoying and bothersome were perceived differently. I self-selected the synonyms to be as semantically similar as possible, and my personal biases may have affected these results. Despite possible bias, the article results suggest that incongruous indefinite articles do not create a barrier to humour perceptions and neither improve nor negate them either.

4.2.1 Indefinite Articles and Error Detection in Verbal and Written Language

Research on error-tracking observed that orthographical errors were least likely to be detected (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p. 1030). Their orthographical errors included 'letter omissions' (Larigauderie et al 2020:1018) which would include a rather than an. Additionally, change blindness

studies support this observation that readers would notice changes to articles less than verb changes (Christensen et al., 2021 as quoted in Soby, Ishkanyan & Kirsten, p. 2023). Logically, incongruous articles may not have been noticed by participants in written language. Therefore, the article results showing neither improvement nor negation in perception may only show a lack of perceiving incongruity.

The meme that inspired this incongruity type to be included was a video of Jeremy Clarkson exclaiming ‘A egg!’ (The Grand Tour, 2022) at a farm, which I could only find as a video and not as a still image. The meme’s lack of popularity as a still image may be a result of nonstandard articles being less noticeable in written language.

The allophones a and an exist for ease of spoken language. Pak (2016, p. 12) observes four variants of the indefinite article in spoken language: ‘/ə/, /ən/, e(j) and either /æn/ or /ɛn/’, depending on what is the most comfortable transition from any previous word to the indefinite article and to the following word. Despite this, only two forms of the article exist orthographically an and a. This indicates that in written language the indefinite article requires less variation and is therefore less noticeable. Thus, incongruous use of the indefinite article in joke-constructions is a topic that needs to be investigated verbally, but not in written language as this research did.

4.3 Plurals

The plural incongruity type may have biases, as aforementioned in the methodology section of this dissertation – these will be considered alongside the analysis in this section. Figure 8 shows the overall results for the plural incongruity type.

Figure 8: Plurals Multiple Choice Question Data.

Figure 8 shows similar results to the gerunds type; the plural incongruity type had a low preference rate with 14% of selection. However, the rating scale data produced three examples where the incongruous form was chosen over its congruous counterpart. Combined, these examples display the difficulty of making plurals incongruous.

Example (8) had a mean rating of 3.5 for (8a), cocktail sausage, and three for (8b), cocktail sausages.

- (8) Oh, that's my mom's friend Carl. He comes over and helps her with plenty of _____.
- cocktail sausage
 - cocktail sausages

Out of 32 respondents for the incongruous form, answer (8a), 19 selected it. Contrastingly, 16 participants out of 23 chose the congruous form in the second question set and 13 out of 25 participants in the last question set. Relative frequency makes this an equal success rate of 59-60% for either option.

Example (9) shows the second and third examples of the higher rated incongruous options.

- (9) I'm not like other children. Toys bore me, and I don't care for sweets, I prefer _____.
- nipple
 - nipples
 - humble earthworm
 - humble earthworms

Answer (9a), nipple, had a mean rating of 3.6 whilst (9b), nipples, had a mean rating of 2.8. Answer (9c), humble earthworm, had a mean rating of three and answer (9d), humble earthworms, had a mean rating of 2.9. The difference between (9c) and (9d) is less of a disparity, with a 0.1 difference, than (9a) and (9b), with a 0.8 difference. It should be noted that example (9) shows a black card question without a quantifying determiner such as plenty of, some, or many which may influence whether participants construed it as incongruous or not.

4.3.1 *Euphemism and the Semantics of Abstract and Proper Nouns*

Shown in the section above, example (8) supports the conclusion that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour if there is a resolution — similarly to the characterisation issue in the gerund section. In example (8), scripts of 'mom', and 'friend' are created — all of which have some sense of responsibility and do not explicitly imply sexual themes. However, sausage is a known euphemism for penis and to say one is receiving lots of sausage in this sense would be to imply they participate in lots of sex, usually with one individual — hence sausage and not sausages. The addition of cocktail to the euphemism, may just work as a determiner of size to the euphemism. If one was using it as a euphemism in this example, as it refers to one individual 'Carl' it would make more semantic sense to use cocktail sausage. Therefore, when the original expectations are confronted by the incongruity, a logical link can be created that the statement is referring to the euphemistic sense rather than the food substance sense. This is an example of a double entendre joke-construction.

Most joke-constructions in the questionnaire did not have a resolution, and grammatically incongruous versions were rated lower and chosen less often than their congruous counterparts. In example (8) answer (8a), nipple, was incongruous but had a possible resolution and it improved perceptions of humour. Therefore, this example would suggest that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour if a semantic resolution is available.

Nipple in its singular form could be construed as an abstract noun. In this sense it could be another euphemism. In the song Greased Lightnin one of the lyrics is: 'we'll be getting lots of tit' (Travolta, 1978). Here, they're referring to seeing or feeling lots of nipples because they are engaging in sexual activity. Thus, in this sense (9a) could be referring to liking lots of sex, whilst (9b) could be referring to liking nipples specifically. If this is the case the semantic incongruity may occur because of the

CHILD script, where respondents may not expect a child to express a committed preference to nipples over sweets and toys. There are two possible semantic resolutions. Firstly, the script of NURSING could be used to suggest the child is expressing preference for being breastfed. Alternatively, the child character could be interpreted as expressing an overtly sexualised interest which would juxtapose the typically innocent CHILD script. Both of these interpretations would constitute a semantic resolution.

Therefore, both (9a), nipple, and (9b), nipples, could be construed as congruous, and thus their results are not representative of absurdist unresolvable grammatical incongruity. Answer (9a), nipple, could be interpreted as an abstract noun and possibly a euphemism and support the earlier conclusion that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour if they contribute to semantic resolution.

Regarding (9c), humble earthworm, and (9d), humble earthworms, it is unlikely they would be interpreted euphemistically. However, it could be construed as an abstract noun. As a singular noun phrase humble earthworm would require an article to make grammatical sense. The lack of article and plurality makes it appear more like a proper noun or abstract noun. However, due to the lack of capitalisation, it is most likely to be construed as an abstract noun.

(10) I'm not like other children. Toys bore me and I don't care for sweets, I prefer

- a. adventure

Example (10) demonstrates an abstract noun in place of humble earthworm. It makes grammatical sense without plurality or an article. If construing humble earthworm as an abstract noun it could refer metaphorically to SIMPLE, NATURAL, and ANTI-MODERNIST, scripts suggesting a desire to return to the natural world as symbolised by the idea of the humble earthworm. Humble earthworm as an answer to example (9) could construct an incongruous scenario where the child exhibits a preference for mundanity and simplicity, which juxtaposes typical interests and desires associated with children. Therefore, the child could appear to the viewer more akin to a wise, old man who has no preference for materialistic desires. The semantic resolution available would then be that the child character is unexpectedly mature for his young age, which could be perceived as amusing. This further indicates that a resolution for why the character speaking is using nonstandard grammar may be significant for grammatical incongruities in joke-constructions to be successful in improving perceptions of humour.

4.4 Key Takeaways

This analysis aimed to answer whether grammatical incongruity improves, negates, or creates a barrier to humour perceptions in joke-constructions. The results indicate that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour if it plays a role in the semantic resolution of the semantic incongruity. The examples of characterisation, euphemism, and abstraction of singular nouns demonstrate that when supporting the semantic resolution grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour.

When the grammatical incongruity did not contribute to semantic incongruity resolution then it worsened perceptions of humour. If the grammatical incongruity was less noticeable via error-detection skills, then the negative impact to perceptions of humour were decreased. Error-detection skills can be affected by several factors such as memory (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p.1032), but generally larger lexical changes like the gerund incongruity type will be most noticeable, followed by incorrect noun type (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p.1030). Nonstandard articles are the least likely to be detected (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p.1030), and this was proven in these results as well.

Additionally, noun changes can impact the sense in which joke-constructions are construed. This research has given some data to suggest that grammatical changes can be influential in the success of joke-constructions that rely on semantic sense, such as the euphemism examples in the plural incongruity type section.

5 Conclusions

Ultimately, this research draws three main conclusions in answer to whether or not grammatical incongruities in fill-in-the-blank joke constructions negates, improves, or creates a barrier to perceptions of humour.

Firstly, grammatical incongruities without resolution do negate perceptions of humour and this is dependent on how noticeable the incongruity is. The less noticeable in accordance with error detection research, the stronger the negation to perceptions of humour. This is shown by the strong correlation between incongruous forms being chosen less often than congruous forms, and the incongruous forms being rated lower than their congruous counterparts. This further suggests that absurdist humour may not work with grammatical absurdities – possibly because it appears to the viewer more like an error than a purposeful decision to not use standard language rules.

This dissertation also investigated whether the grammatical incongruity trend found in memes could be successful in a different medium. Thus, these results do not necessarily reflect the correlation between incongruity and humour perception in meme joke-constructions. There does appear to be a difference between the success of grammatical incongruity types on improving perceptions of humour in memes and fill-in-the-blank written joke constructions. This is suggested by the Doge (NovaXP, 2014) and Happy Cat (Menning, 2010) memes and the gerund results, as despite their popularity the incongruity type was the least preferable out of the three. This could be due to the digital medium used — as aforementioned, memes use more spoken language conventions, but a questionnaire would act more similarly to a webpage and use more written language conventions. As described in the gerund sub-section of the data section, the characters speaking, and the spoken language conventions could mean that the grammatical incongruities are not incongruous in their medium context. On the other hand, in the questionnaire they certainly would be viewed this way. Further studies could examine this further by testing different mediums and doing a cross-comparative study, or by using a meme-based game as the framework such as *What Do You Meme?* (Tebele & Kaplan, 2016).

Another conclusion of this dissertation is that the incongruity type used affects the results. As aforementioned, error-tracking research leads me to believe that less noticeable grammatical incongruities are less likely to create a barrier to perceptions of humour. However, this then suggests that grammatical incongruities do create a barrier because if they go unnoticed their incongruity is inconsequential. Alternatively, this conclusion also points out that some features of grammar are more flexible than others and that participants may construe them differently, as exemplified by the difference for noun types.

As I was not purposefully testing for this, a limitation of this research is that incongruity types were not based on error-tracking in design, although the clear links between error-tracking and which incongruity types received more or less preference suggests this to be a less impactful limitation. Further investigation into this conclusion including more varied incongruity types may provide more information. Additionally, error-tracking is affected by many factors such as memory (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p. 1032). As the sample was not assessed on the factors that could skew this, it is not an appropriate conclusion for the scope of this project and further research may be required to validate the claim, once again though the clear correlation makes this a less-impactful limitation.

Additionally, unintentional congruous construal should be considered for further research, as in the case for the plurals section of this dissertation as this could affect results and was a limitation for this research. Furthermore, if a meme format was used in future research, then limiting the options to verbal or written incongruities, or testing them separately, would be beneficial. The article incongruity type demonstrates the drastic change in results that not taking this into account can cause.

This dissertation concludes that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour when it plays a role in resolving the semantic incongruity of a joke-construction. The examples of characterisation and euphemism in the gerund and plural incongruity types demonstrate that when a semantic resolution is available, perceptions of humour can be improved by deviances from standard grammatical choices. In the case of memes, visual elements can provide an additional layer of context that can provide resolution to grammatical incongruity. One of the research questions was whether grammatical incongruity could improve perceptions of humour in different mediums, and I can conclude that it can if a semantic resolution is available.

In the three case study memes All Your Base are Belong to Us (Dubs, 2009), Happy Cat (Menning, 2010), and Doge (NovaXP, 2014), the grammatical incongruities are resolvable, as I resolved in the early part of this dissertation. Therefore, there is a consistent observation that resolvable grammatical incongruities may improve perceptions to humour, both in real world examples and in this research. This leads to another question, does semantic sense/resolution make grammatical incongruities appear congruous because the purpose of grammar changes in these joke-constructions? This would be an interesting further study not just for the study of humour but for semanticists generally.

Additionally, Crystal (2019, p. 97) notes that ‘There are hundreds of meme wannabes on the Internet now, all hoping (but few achieving) a permanent place in language history. Some sites provide instructions on ‘how to create your own meme’. We must expect a significant increase in the amount of linguistic idiosyncrasy both on and off the web now, srsly.’ Whilst my research sought to investigate whether this trend appeared outside of meme joke-constructions, this argues that this trend may no longer be popular and as such joke-constructions using the trend may negate perceptions of humour. Further studies could compare the online popularity of memes with nonstandard grammar across the last two decades to determine whether this trend has fallen out of fashion.

Overall, these results and conclusions contribute to a final thought: despite looking for the effect of grammatical incongruity I have resolved that at the level of linguistic features, language is so flexible that it can often be made congruous despite incongruous design. Linking back to Attardo’s definition of humour, if an individual can create a semantic link and make a construction make sense to them, even if it appears absurd, then it can be perceived humorously.

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